

Large language models empower meta-analysis in the big data era

Owen Sun¹, Michelle Cheuk², Hojin Moon^{2*}

2025 Joint Statistical Meetings Proceedings

¹California Academy of Mathematics and Science

1000 E. Victoria St., Carson, CA 90747

² Department of Mathematics and Statistics, California State University, Long Beach

1250 Bellflower Blvd., Long Beach, CA 90840

*Correspondence: hojin.moon@csulb.edu

Abstract:

Background: In the current big data era, large data repositories containing thousands of studies present opportunities for meta-analysis but require labor-intensive, time-consuming screening.

Methods: We evaluated four large language models (LLMs) in a zero-shot setting to screen 536 studies from the NCBI Gene Expression Omnibus, comparing their screening decisions with those of two human reviewers. LLMs were provided dataset titles, descriptions, and clinical data and were asked to determine and justify screening decisions based on inclusion/exclusion criteria for a meta-analysis on adjuvant chemotherapy recommendation.

Results: Following prompt engineering, GPT-4.1-mini, GPT-5-mini, and o4-mini achieved 92% sensitivity (11/12) with high specificity (96.8%-99.2%). GPT-5-mini achieved 99.1% accuracy and an F1 score of 0.815, the highest among the LLMs evaluated.

Conclusions: LLMs can substantially reduce dataset screening effort for meta-analysis while maintaining human-level sensitivity. To support reproducibility, we developed an application implementing our methodology for LLM-based screening of GEO studies and released all code publicly.

Introduction:

Following the widespread adoption of FAIR guidelines for scientific data management, scientific data repositories such as the NCBI's Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) now contain hundreds of thousands of study datasets and are continuing to grow, with GEO expected to double in size every five years^{1,2}. While synthesizing these vast amounts of data through meta-analysis may yield more robust or novel discoveries, the sheer volume of potentially relevant datasets makes comprehensive manual screening increasingly challenging and notoriously time-consuming, often taking weeks to months to complete^{1,3}. To reduce screening load, investigators often narrow search queries, a tradeoff that can completely exclude relevant studies by failing to identify them for screening⁴.

In the FAIR schema, this presents a growing findability challenge. For two decades, researchers have explored automating or partially automating study screening for systematic reviews, resulting in the emergence of four approaches: screening prioritization, text classification, active learning, and reinforcement learning⁵. Among these approaches, active learning approaches have been most deployed in software, as evaluated in a systematic review from Ofori-Boateng et al.⁵. These active learning approaches, involving human reviewers classifying a sample of studies for use as training data for classification models screening unreviewed studies, include ASReview⁶, Abstrackr⁷, Colandr⁸, and Rayyan⁹. In title screening for one systematic review on interventional

impacts on musculoskeletal pain and disability, Rayyan, Abstrackr, and Colandr demonstrated fair sensitivity (65-78%) and near-perfect specificity (99%)¹⁰.

Shortly after the release of GPT-3.5 (the first version of ChatGPT) in late 2022, large language models (LLMs) have begun to emerge as a possible new approach to aid study screening¹¹. In the biomedical domain in particular, studies evaluating LLMs for study screening are emerging and include Oami et al. (2024), Dai et al. (2025), and Homiar et al. (2025)¹²⁻¹⁴. More broadly in the literature, Lieberum et al. found 14 articles utilizing LLMs for study selection out of 37 articles using LLMs anywhere in the systematic review process in a scoping review through February 2024¹¹. Among those 14 articles validating study screening, most performed title and abstract screening and the majority of those studies had the sentiment that applying LLMs for study screening was “promising.”¹¹ However, challenges remain, including the sensitivity of LLMs to variation in word choice in prompts, response variation in non-deterministic LLMs such as in ‘reasoning’ models, inconsistent response formatting which can lead to downstream parsing errors, and the necessity for additional validation studies^{11,15}.

While recent work has focused on applying LLMs to screening the scientific literature, to our knowledge, there has been limited exploration of applying LLMs to screen datasets within biomedical data repositories, a necessary step when identifying studies to include in meta-analysis. In this article, we contribute a case study demonstrating the use of LLMs for dataset screening in the NCBI Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) biomedical data repository. In GEO, we screen studies in a meta-analysis on adjuvant chemotherapy recommendation in early-stage non-small cell lung cancer — an area of clinical controversy, utilizing unstructured dataset titles and descriptions in combination with the dataset’s clinical data in LLM dataset screening.

Methods:

Study identification using a broad search query

To identify as many potentially relevant study datasets as possible for further screening, we utilized broad search queries, seeking to capture all studies on a topic (e.g., all studies on lung cancer) in the data repository for further screening with the LLM. Oftentimes, these broad search queries can return hundreds to thousands of studies. While many identified studies may not be relevant to the research question at hand, it reduces the likelihood of completely missing potentially relevant studies.

In the lung cancer case study, we queried the Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) for all available expression array studies containing the keywords “NSCLC” or “non-small cell lung cancer” through December 2024.

Collect dataset-specific context for screening

Following study identification, additional context for each dataset, including dataset titles and descriptions, were programmatically collected to facilitate screening decisions. For datasets in GEO, titles and descriptions were accessed using the NCBI’s Entrez Programming Utilities API through the Bio.Entrez module of the Python library *Biopython* (Biopython version: 1.85; Python version: 3.10.9)^{16,17}. Additionally, clinical data accessible with the GEO2r tool were programmatically accessed using the Python library *Selenium* (version: 4.27.1)¹⁸. If a GEO dataset contained multiple platforms, clinical data from each platform was collected. The context, i.e. the title, description, and clinical data, for each GEO study was saved to a single CSV file for screening.

Inclusion and exclusion screening criteria

To determine if a study should be evaluated by human reviewers, the LLM screens studies according to investigator-defined inclusion and exclusion criteria using study titles, descriptions, and, in the case of GEO, clinical data. Studies passing screening may be evaluated by human reviewers, together with associated full-text reports, in line with PRISMA 2020 systematic review guidelines¹⁹.

In the lung cancer case study, dataset titles, descriptions, and clinical data are provided to each LLM and requested to review each study based on the following inclusion/exclusion criteria. Studies were requested to be included if there was 1) presence of patient-specific survival time and status variables (e.g., overall survival or progression-free survival) and 2) at least one of the following: a) sample composition of at least 50% stage I patients; or b) explicit adjuvant chemotherapy annotation. Datasets meeting these criteria were requested to be included by the LLM while those not meeting the criteria were excluded. To provide ground truth, human reviewers used the same screening criteria.

Large language model-aided study screening

We utilize the following LLMs: gpt-4o-mini-2024-07-18, gpt-4.1-mini-2025-04-14, o4-mini-2025-04-16, and gpt-5-mini-2025-08-07 models via the OpenAI API's Chat Completions endpoint. All models' versions were constant throughout data collection. Temperature was set to zero to ensure determinism and reproducibility in "chat" models (i.e., GPT-4o-mini and GPT-4.1-mini). The temperature of o4-mini, a reasoning model, was set to the minimum temperature of 1.0 for more deterministic responses and had a seed set to 42 to ensure response reproducibility. GPT-5-mini, another reasoning model, had a seed set to 42 but did not support adjusting temperature

nor a top_p parameter to increase determinism. Reasoning effort for GPT-5-mini was set to the medium effort, the default. All prompts were zero-shot, meaning that no example screening evaluation was provided to the model in the prompt. Batch requests were used to minimize API costs.

An LLM prompt subdivides into two messages: system (also known as developer) messages and user messages²⁰. The system message provides overarching instructions, such as response styling and formatting, and take precedence over user messages. In the system message, we utilized expert role-play prompting (“you are an oncology expert...”) and requested the LLM to evaluate each study based on inclusion/exclusion criteria provided in the user message. To ensure ease of downstream response parsing, the system message requested the model to refrain from restating questions, nor combine answers to separate questions, and respond in the same numbered list format as the questions were posed in the user prompt²¹. The user prompt contained inclusion/exclusion criteria, study-specific metadata (e.g., clinical data, title, and description for GEO studies), and paired reasoning and decision questions for each criterion. By requesting reasoning before each decision and asking the model to “think step by step,” we aimed to stimulate chain-of-thought, increasing interpretability and accuracy²¹. After prompting the model to evaluate each inclusion/exclusion criterion, the model was asked to justify whether the provided study should be included before returning a final inclusion decision. Each study was evaluated independently by the LLM in individual requests.

Upon the return of LLM responses as a JSON Lines (.jsonl) file, responses are parsed using regular expressions to extract responses to each question in the returned numbered list. Extracted responses are then saved in a CSV file for ease of review and identification of selected studies.

Human verification and evaluation

Two independent human reviewers screened the studies, using titles, descriptions, and, only for GEO studies, clinical data from GEO2R, in accordance with the inclusion/exclusion criteria to evaluate the LLMs' screening decisions. Interrater reliability was evaluated using Cohen's kappa and Prevalence-Adjusted Bias-Adjusted Kappa (PABAK)^{22,23}. Decision disagreements were resolved through discussion. Using human reviews as the ground truth, sensitivity (recall), specificity, precision (positive predictive value), accuracy, and F1 score of the LLM reviews are calculated. Confusion matrices and ROC curves are used to evaluate the alignment of LLM and human screening decisions.

Prompt engineering

As initial prompts are often suboptimal and LLMs depend on precise instructions²⁴, we iteratively optimized the prompt by qualitatively evaluating LLM responses that diverged from human decisions, particularly false negative decisions — where the model failed to correctly include a study. We focused on false negative decision as excluding decisions would be detrimental to the downstream analysis by making the screening less than comprehensive. Each divergent decision was evaluated by reviewing the model's decision and justification for each inclusion/exclusion criterion. Accordingly, we revised the prompt to address phrase ambiguities or cases not considered in the inclusion/exclusion criteria. The prompt iterations for each case study are shown in Supplementary Materials alongside the causes for revision.

Figure 1. Modified PRISMA Flowchart for LLM-aided Study Screening with GPT-5-mini

Results:

Human inclusion/exclusion screening

The NCBI GEO search query identified 536 studies. Subsequent screening by two independent human reviewers resulted in the selection of 12 studies out of 536 studies considered. Interrater reliability, evaluated with Cohen's kappa and PABAK, were 0.900 and 0.985, respectively.

LLM screening performance

Initially, screening by GPT-4.1-mini identified 20 studies, GPT-4o-mini identified 26, GPT-5-mini identified 18 studies, and o4-mini identified 18 studies. Using human screening as a benchmark, LLM screening demonstrated varying sensitivity, with the highest sensitivity of 92% (11/12) by o4-mini and GPT-5-mini, followed by GPT-4.1-mini with 83% sensitivity (10/12), and GPT-4o-mini with 75% sensitivity (9/12). Specificity was high across all LLMs, ranging between 98.7% (517/524; GPT-5-mini and o4-mini) and 96.8% (507/524; GPT-4o-mini). Confusion matrices are available in Figures S1-S3 in Supplementary Materials.

After qualitative review of LLM screening responses, the system prompt was simplified to only include response styling instructions, moving inclusion/exclusion criteria to the user prompt. The review found that LLMs sometimes incorrectly included studies that mentioned survival in study descriptions despite lack of survival time and status in the dataset. The prompt's first question was revised to request survival variables, specifically, not just "data." As this revision did not eliminate misclassification based on the survival variable, the first question was further revised to require "explicit, patient-specific" survival data and clarified that mention of survival in free-form text was insufficient to meet the criteria. Accordingly, in the third and final prompt, the word "or" in the inclusion/exclusion section of the user prompt was emphasized with capitalization and double asterisks.

Following two rounds of prompt optimization, GPT-5-mini, o4-mini, and GPT-4.1-mini achieved high sensitivity of 92% (11/12). GPT-4o-mini had sensitivity of 83.3% (10/12). Specificity remained high at 99.2% (520/524) for GPT-5-mini, 98.9% (518/524) for o4-mini, 97.7% (512/524) by GPT-4o-mini, and 96.8% (507/524) by GPT-4.1-mini in the final prompt. False positives between the initial and final prompt increased from 10 to 17 for GPT-4.1-mini

but decreased slightly for o4-mini with 7 false positives initially and 6 false positives in the final prompt. GPT-4o-mini had false positives decrease from 17 in the first prompt to 12 in the third prompt. GPT-5-mini also demonstrated a reduction in false positives from 7 to 4 after the third prompt. Accordingly, precision declined for GPT-4.1-mini (v1: 0.500; v3: 0.393) and increased for GPT-4o-mini (v1: 0.346; v3: 0.455), o4-mini (v1: 0.611; v3: 0.647), and GPT-5-mini (v1: 0.611; v3: 0.733). Between the first and final prompt, accuracy increased from 98.5% to 99.1% for GPT-5-mini, increased from 96.3% to 97.4% for GPT-4o-mini, remained stable for o4-mini (v1: 98.5%; v3: 98.7%), and declined by 1.2% for GPT-4.1-mini (v1: 97.8%, v3: 96.6%). F1 scores increased from 0.733 to 0.815 for GPT-5-mini, increased from 0.474 to 0.588 for GPT-4o-mini, increased slightly for o4-mini (v1: 0.733; v3: 0.759), and decreased from 0.625 to 0.550 for GPT-4.1-mini. Screening performance of LLMs across prompt versions and models is shown in Figure 2. Table S1 in the Supplementary Materials lists all performance metrics in tabular form.

Figure 2. Performance of LLMs for GEO Dataset Screening Across Prompt Versions

Discussion:

LLMs were highly specific and sensitive at screening GEO datasets, indicating great promise for significantly reducing human workload associated with screening datasets in big data repositories. Of the LLMs we evaluated, GPT-5-mini performed best, achieving 99.1% accuracy and an F1 score of 0.815.

In the case study presented, LLM screening was on par with human screening sensitivity, with three of four LLMs evaluated (GPT-4.1-mini, o4-mini, and GPT-5-mini) identifying 11 of 12 studies selected by human reviewers. The twelfth study contained ambiguous staging, stating that patients were “early stage,” and was included by human reviewers for full-text review but were excluded by LLMs. We found that the LLMs were generally highly adherent to instructions and sometimes may not demonstrate the nuance or flexibility of human reviewers in the face of ambiguity.

Prompt engineering increased the clarity and specificity of the screening requests (Supplementary Figure S4), resulting in improved sensitivity, particularly for GPT-4.1-mini. While our shared prompt engineering procedure allowed for head-to-head comparisons, and improved screening performance for some models, it led to slightly worse performance in others, indicating that the prompts used may not be optimal for each model²¹. Notably, o4-mini and GPT-5-mini, both reasoning models and newer than the GPT-4.1-mini and GPT-4o-mini models, achieved high sensitivity and specificity in the first prompt version and performed similarly across prompt versions, indicating that they were perhaps less reliant on prompt wording to achieve high screening accuracy.

In practice, using LLMs to reduce screening workload while ensuring accurate screening decisions will likely require human reviewers to randomly sample and screen studies to ensure

no systemic misclassifications. Accordingly, additional investigation is warranted to develop reliable and effective workflows for prospective use of LLMs in screening, such as power analyses to recommend the minimum number of studies that human reviewers should screen.

In our study, common causes of misclassification included the LLMs confusing mention of survival or related terms, such as hazard ratios, in titles or descriptions with presence of survival time and status variables in the data. Other causes included presence of survival variables or staging variables in the datasets that the LLM failed to identify. Misclassifications also arose due to incorrect conclusions on the sample proportion of Stage I patients, particularly for proportions very close to 50% (e.g., 48%). In future implementations, this may be mitigated by allowing the use of coding tools, so LLMs can develop code to explicitly count proportions. These misclassifications indicate the necessity of human review of LLM screening decisions.

Limitations remain. The broad search query we utilized did not include additional NSCLC-related keywords such as “lung adenocarcinoma” or “lung squamous cell carcinoma” which would have made the search more comprehensive. This was done to limit the manual burden required to screen additional studies due to limited personnel resources. Additional investigation is necessary to evaluate LLMs for search queries with more studies, perhaps by comparing LLMs’ screening performance against existing high-quality meta-analyses.

Overall, LLMs are highly capable of screening datasets, comparable to human screening, in NCBI GEO and have promise for accelerating scientific discovery by significantly reducing human workload needed to screen studies for meta-analysis.

Data Availability:

All data used in this study are publicly available at the NCBI Gene Expression Omnibus:

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gds/>.

Code Availability:

We implemented the methodology used in this study for screening GEO studies with LLMs in a user-friendly Python-based application. The application and all code are available on GitHub at

<https://github.com/osun24/geo-llm>.

References:

1. Clough, E. *et al.* NCBI GEO: archive for gene expression and epigenomics data sets: 23-year update. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **52**, D138–D144 (2024).
2. Wilkinson, M. D. *et al.* The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci. Data* **3**, (2016).
3. Haddaway, N. R. & Westgate, M. J. Predicting the time needed for environmental systematic reviews and systematic maps. *Conserv. Biol.* **33**, 434–443 (2019).
4. O'Mara-Eves, A., Thomas, J., McNaught, J., Miwa, M. & Ananiadou, S. Using text mining for study identification in systematic reviews: a systematic review of current approaches. *Syst. Rev.* **4**, 5 (2015).
5. Ofori-Boateng, R., Aceves-Martins, M., Wiratunga, N. & Moreno-Garcia, C. F. Towards the automation of systematic reviews using natural language processing, machine learning, and deep learning: a comprehensive review. *Artif. Intell. Rev.* **57**, 200 (2024).

6. van de Schoot, R. *et al.* An open source machine learning framework for efficient and transparent systematic reviews. *Nat. Mach. Intell.* **3**, 125–133 (2021).
7. Wallace, B. C., Small, K., Brodley, C. E., Lau, J. & Trikalinos, T. A. Deploying an interactive machine learning system in an evidence-based practice center: abstractkr. in *Proceedings of the 2nd ACM SIGHIT International Health Informatics Symposium* 819–824 (ACM, Miami Florida USA, 2012). doi:10.1145/2110363.2110464.
8. Cheng, S. H. *et al.* Using machine learning to advance synthesis and use of conservation and environmental evidence. *Conserv. Biol.* **32**, 762–764 (2018).
9. Ouzzani, M., Hammady, H., Fedorowicz, Z. & Elmagarmid, A. Rayyan—a web and mobile app for systematic reviews. *Syst. Rev.* **5**, 210 (2016).
10. Dos Reis, A. H. S. *et al.* Usefulness of machine learning softwares to screen titles of systematic reviews: a methodological study. *Syst. Rev.* **12**, 68 (2023).
11. Lieberum, J.-L. *et al.* Large language models for conducting systematic reviews: on the rise, but not yet ready for use—a scoping review. *J. Clin. Epidemiol.* **181**, 111746 (2025).
12. Homiar, A. *et al.* Development and evaluation of prompts for a large language model to screen titles and abstracts in a living systematic review. *BMJ Ment. Health* **28**, e301762 (2025).
13. Dai, Z.-Y. *et al.* Accuracy of Large Language Models for Literature Screening in Thoracic Surgery: Diagnostic Study. *J. Med. Internet Res.* **27**, e67488 (2025).
14. Oami, T., Okada, Y. & Nakada, T. Performance of a Large Language Model in Screening Citations. *JAMA Netw. Open* **7**, e2420496 (2024).

15. Delgado-Chaves, F. M. *et al.* Transforming literature screening: The emerging role of large language models in systematic reviews. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* **122**, e2411962122 (2025).
16. Entrez Programming Utilities Help.
17. Cock, P. J. A. *et al.* Biopython: freely available Python tools for computational molecular biology and bioinformatics. *Bioinformatics* **25**, 1422–1423 (2009).
18. Selenium. SeleniumHQ.
19. Page, M. J. *et al.* The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* n71 (2021) doi:10.1136/bmj.n71.
20. Prompt engineering - OpenAI API. <https://platform.openai.com>.
21. Chen, B., Zhang, Z., Langrené, N. & Zhu, S. Unleashing the potential of prompt engineering for large language models. *Patterns* 101260 (2025) doi:10.1016/j.patter.2025.101260.
22. Cohen, J. A Coefficient of Agreement for Nominal Scales. *Educ. Psychol. Meas.* **20**, 37–46 (1960).
23. Byrt, T., Bishop, J. & Carlin, J. B. Bias, prevalence and kappa. *J. Clin. Epidemiol.* **46**, 423–429 (1993).
24. Russe, M. F., Reisert, M., Bamberg, F. & Rau, A. Improving the use of LLMs in radiology through prompt engineering: from precision prompts to zero-shot learning. *RöFo - Fortschritte Auf Dem Geb. Röntgenstrahlen Bildgeb. Verfahr.* **196**, 1166–1170 (2024).

Author Contributions:

Conceptualization: O.S.; Methodology: O.S., H.M.; Software: O.S.; Validation: O.S., M.C.; Investigation: O.S., M.C.; Writing - Original Draft: O.S.; Writing - Review & Editing: O.S., M.C., H.M.; Visualization: O.S.; Supervision: H.M.

Competing Interests:

The authors declare no competing interests.

Funding:

The authors did not receive funding from any organization for the submitted work.

Ethics Statement:

As this study only used de-identified, publicly available data from the NCBI Gene Expression, ethical approval was not required.

Supplementary Materials:

Performance of LLMs for GEO Dataset Screening Across Prompt Versions

Model	Version	Sensitivity	Specificity	Precision	Accuracy	F1 Score	TP	FP	TN	FN
GPT-4.1-mini	v1	0.833	0.981	0.500	0.978	0.625	10	10	514	2
GPT-4.1-mini	v2	0.917	0.969	0.407	0.968	0.564	11	16	508	1
GPT-4.1-mini	v3	0.917	0.968	0.393	0.966	0.550	11	17	507	1
GPT-4o-mini	v1	0.750	0.968	0.346	0.963	0.474	9	17	507	3
GPT-4o-mini	v2	0.833	0.968	0.370	0.965	0.513	10	17	507	2
GPT-4o-mini	v3	0.833	0.977	0.455	0.974	0.588	10	12	512	2
GPT-5-mini	v1	0.917	0.987	0.611	0.985	0.733	11	7	517	1
GPT-5-mini	v2	0.917	0.987	0.611	0.985	0.733	11	7	517	1
GPT-5-mini	v3	0.917	0.992	0.733	0.991	0.815	11	4	520	1
o4-mini	v1	0.917	0.987	0.611	0.985	0.733	11	7	517	1
o4-mini	v2	0.833	0.989	0.625	0.985	0.714	10	6	518	2
o4-mini	v3	0.917	0.989	0.647	0.987	0.759	11	6	518	1

Supplementary Table 1. Performance of LLMs for GEO Dataset Screening Across Prompt Versions

Confusion Matrices by Model for GEO Dataset Screening

Supplementary Figure 1. Screening Confusion Matrix by LLM for Prompt Version 1

Confusion Matrices by Model for GEO Dataset Screening

Supplementary Figure 2. Screening Confusion Matrix by LLM for Prompt Version 2

Confusion Matrices by Model for GEO Dataset Screening

Supplementary Figure 3. Screening Confusion Matrix by LLM for Prompt Version 3

Lung Cancer Case Study: Prompt Optimization Iterations

Added Removed Unchanged

A. v1 (baseline)

SYSTEM:

You are an expert in analyzing clinical datasets for inclusion in a meta-analysis building ML survival models for adjuvant chemotherapy (ACT) treatment recommendation in NSCLC (non-small cell lung cancer). Your task is to determine whether the provided dataset includes survival status and time data and either of the following: adjuvant chemotherapy (ACT) status data OR includes a majority of patients (>50%) with Stage I NSCLC for inclusion in the meta-analysis.

USER:

The dataset below contains clinical information for NSCLC patients. Let's think step by step and answer the following:

1. Does the dataset include survival status and time data (e.g., OS, RFS, PFS)? If so, please specify.
2. Does it include a majority of patients (>50%) with Stage I NSCLC? If so, please specify.
3. Does it include adjuvant chemotherapy (ACT) status data? If so, please specify.
4. Briefly justify if this dataset should be considered for inclusion in the meta-analysis in 1 sentence.
5. Should this dataset be considered for inclusion in the meta-analysis? (Answer "Yes" or "No.")

B. v1 → v2

SYSTEM:

You are an oncology expert ~~in analyzing~~ evaluating clinical datasets ~~for based inclusion~~ on inclusion/exclusion criteria. Respond concisely and clearly, returning answers in ~~a the meta-analysis~~ same building numbered ML list survival format ~~models for~~ adjuvant the chemotherapy questions.

USER:

A ~~(ACT) clinical treatment recommendation in NSCLC (non-small non-small cell lung cancer) cancer~~ Your (NSCLC) ~~task~~ dataset, ~~is its title, determine and whether~~ description ~~the are provided~~ included below. Inclusion Criteria:

1. The dataset ~~includes~~ must include patients' survival status and time ~~data~~ variables ~~and (e.g., either~~ OS, RFS, PFS).
And one or both of the following:
- 2a. ~~adjuvant~~ The chemotherapy dataset (ACT) ~~must status data OR includes~~ include a majority of patients (>50%) with Stage I ~~NSCLC~~ NSCLC.
- 2b. ~~for inclusion in the meta-analysis:~~

USER:

The dataset ~~below~~ must ~~contains~~ include ~~clinical~~ adjuvant ~~information~~ chemotherapy for (ACT) NSCLC status ~~patients~~ data.

Let's think step by step and answer the following:

1. Does the dataset include survival status variable and survival time ~~data~~ variable (e.g., OS, RFS, PFS)? If so, please ~~specify~~ specify the variables.
2. Does it include a majority of patients (>50%) with Stage I NSCLC? If so, please ~~specify~~ explain.
3. Does it include adjuvant chemotherapy (ACT) status data? If so, please ~~specify~~ explain.
4. Briefly justify if this dataset should be considered for inclusion in the meta-analysis in 1 sentence.
5. Should this dataset be considered for inclusion in the meta-analysis? (Answer "Yes" or "No.")

C. v2 → v3

SYSTEM:

You are an oncology expert evaluating clinical datasets based on inclusion/exclusion criteria. Respond concisely and clearly, returning answers in the same numbered list format as the questions.

USER:

A clinical non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) dataset, its title, and description are included below. Inclusion Criteria:

1. The dataset must include ~~patients'~~ explicit, patient-specific survival status and time variables (e.g., OS, RFS, PFS). ~~Mere mention of survival in title or description is inadequate to meet this criterion.~~
And one ~~or~~ OR both of the following:
- 2a. The dataset must include a majority of patients (>50%) with Stage I NSCLC.
- 2b. The dataset must include adjuvant chemotherapy (ACT) status data.

Let's think step by step and answer the following:

1. Does the dataset include survival status variable and survival time variable (e.g., OS, RFS, PFS)? If so, please specify the variables.
2. Does it include a majority of patients (>50%) with Stage I NSCLC? If so, please explain.
3. Does it include adjuvant chemotherapy (ACT) status data? If so, please explain.
4. Briefly justify if this dataset should be considered for inclusion in the meta-analysis in 1 sentence.
5. Should this dataset be considered for inclusion in the meta-analysis? (Answer "Yes" or "No.")

Supplementary Figure 4. Changes Between Prompt Iterations During Prompt Engineering

LLM Study Screening: NCBI GEO

Project Settings

Project Name:

NCBI Search Settings

Search Query:

Max Entries to Fetch:

Batch Job Settings

System Prompt:

User Prompt:

Queries:

[Add Question](#)

[Fetch NCBI Data](#) [Process GEO Data](#) [Create Batch Job](#) [Get Last Batch](#)

.....

Progress: 0%

Supplementary Figure 6. User Interface of Our Application for Screening GEO Studies with an

LLM